

Impact Metamorphic Pyroxene in Anorthosite: Implications for the Evolution of Lunar Highland Crust.

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Introduction: The lunar anorthosite crust is a major geological unit on the Moon. Mafic minerals within anorthosite crust, such as pyroxene, provide crucial compositional and microstructural evidence for reconstructing the crust's formation and evolutionary history. For instance, the presence of both low-Ca and high-Ca pyroxenes (LCP and HCP) in highland anorthosites suggests a multilayered crustal structure (LCP anorthosite: 1–4 km, HCP anorthosite and pure anorthosite: ~20–30 km)^[1–2]. Nevertheless, the origin of this layering whether through endogenic processes like a magma ocean or exogenic impact modification remains debated. The Chang'E-6 (CE-6) mission successfully returned farside lunar soils composed of lithic and glassy materials shaped by endogenic and exogenic processes, including crustal differentiation, volcanic activity, impact events, and space weathering^[3]. Pyroxene, a common mineral in both lunar basaltic and feldspathic samples, serves as a key indicator of magmatic evolution and impact-related modifications^[4, 5]. In this study, we examined shock-altered augite clasts within anorthosite breccias from the CE-6 samples, revealing a suite of deformation and alteration features: shock-induced lamellar twinning, thermally driven recrystallization (yielding granular augite with inherited crystallographic orientations), and localized dissociation products (Fe-metal and fayalite). These features collectively record a transition from transient high-pressure deformation to prolonged high-temperature alteration. Furthermore, the recrystallized augite granules exhibit elevated alumina contents (>8 wt%), indicating intergranular diffusion between augite and plagioclase. This process likely occurred within a large-scale impact melt lake, where slow cooling from ~1300 to 900 °C over several thousand years preserved these signatures. These findings provide critical insights into the thermal evolution of major impact basins, such as the Apollo Basin at the CE-6 landing site, and underscore the role of impact processes in modifying lunar crustal materials.

Samples and Methods: This study focused on five anorthosite breccias (200–300 μm in size) extracted from the CE-6 lunar soil sample (CE6C0200YJFM003). To characterize their microstructures and compositions, we employed a multi-technique analytical approach, including: Backscattered electron (BSE), electron backscattered diffraction (EBSD), electron probe microanalysis (EPMA), Kikuchi diffraction (TKD) and scanning transmission electron microscope (STEM).

Results: The five anorthosite breccias exhibit similar lithology, consisting predominantly of plagioclase (86.9–92.3 vol%) and pyroxene (7.7–13.1 vol%), with minor accessory phases (<1 vol%) including ilmenite, fayalite, and Fe-metal/oxides. Most augite clasts display granular textures composed of 1–10 μm subgrains while retaining angular to irregular outlines, all showing characteristically high Al₂O₃ (>8 wt%) but low Na₂O (<0.3 wt%) contents. Adjacent augite granules exhibit twin relationships involving 180° rotation around <001> with (100) twin planes, while some clasts locally preserve lamellar (100) twins. Vermicular to dendritic fayalite grains with interstitial material occur sporadically within pyroxene clasts, occasionally containing ~1 μm Fe-metal particles.

The Ca-rich domains (augite) situate adjacent to the fayalite regions showing high CaO contents and low Mg# values, whereas the Ca-poor domains (pigeonite) that are located away from the fayalite regions show the opposite trend revealed by low CaO contents and high Mg# values (Fig. 1C, F, I, and K). More Ca-rich domains in completely granular pyroxene are observed compared with the partially granular pyroxene (Fig. 1C, F, I and K).

Fig.1 Microstructures and compositions of pyroxene and plagioclase clasts.

Discussions and significances: Morphological, crystallographic, and compositional analyses of pyroxenes in CE-6 anorthosite breccias reveal a multi-stage impact history recorded in the lunar soil. The earliest stage involved an impact-generated anorthositic melt, from which high-Al pyroxenes initially crystallized. Subsequent impact event(s) then im-

posed mechanical deformation, evidenced by twin formation, and induced post-shock thermal metamorphism. This later thermal event drove exsolution and recrystallization, altering the primary igneous textures and compositions, and producing granular pyroxene, dissociation of fayalite, and liberation of metallic iron. This process provides a petrogenetic mechanism for the formation of high-calcium pyroxene (HCP) within anorthosite, thereby contributing to the lithological evolution of the lunar highland crust.

References: [1] Yamamoto S et al. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, 2015, 120, 831-848. [2] Xu G et al. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, 2025, 130, e2025JE009323. [3] Li C et al. *National Science Review*, 2024, 1: nwae328. [4] Leroux H et al. *Meteoritics & Planetary Science*, 2004, 39(5): 711-722. [5] Daly L et al. *Science Advances*, 2019, 5(9): eaaw5549.